

Ways of Expressing a Presupposition

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Abstract: In language, lexical presupposition is related to the meaning of the lexeme. Some lexical units directly express presupposition within a sentence, while others require examination in their broader context. In the Uzbek language, lexical units, due to their abstract nature, gain new meanings in speech, which distinguishes them from other linguistic elements.

INTRODUCTION

For this reason, the semantic characteristics of some lexical units cannot always be determined solely by the context or speech situation. These lexemes, whose meanings become clearer through pragmatic analysis, should be studied in connection with the context and the speech environment. This research focuses on identifying the essence of presupposition by analyzing lexical units within sentence contexts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It is well-known that the semantic aspects of many lexical units become evident during the speech process. The verbal meanings, optional meaning components, and evaluative frameworks of lexical units emerge in speech. Additionally, lexical units can be assigned supplementary communicative-pragmatic roles during the speech process, further expanding their semantic-functional capabilities. Any additional roles assigned to lexical units are determined by the context and the speech situation. This highlights the need to study lexical units from a pragmatic perspective, particularly to assess their potential for expressing various presuppositions. In the Uzbek language, based on the semantic properties of certain lexical units and the general knowledge of the speakers about the subject, these units can be tasked with conveying presuppositions during speech. Some lexical units naturally express presuppositions due to their inherent semantic properties, while others are assigned this role based on their semantic-functional characteristics. Accordingly, lexical units expressing presuppositions can be categorized into different types.

- a) lexical units specific to the expression of presupposition;
- b) lexical units responsible for expressing presuppositions in speech.

Lexical units of the first type are those that inherently express presuppositions due to their lexical characteristics. When these units are used in a sentence, presuppositions are triggered by their lexical meanings or through their facultative meanings, synonymy, antonymy, or ambiguity. For instance, in the sentence "He dried his shirt," the presupposition that "His shirt was wet" arises. This presupposition is derived from the semantic component of "wet," which is part of the dictionary definition of *dry*, meaning "to be wet and become free from moisture."

L.A. Numova illustrates this with the example of the sentence "Закройте дверь" ("Close the door"), where the presupposition that the door was open is based on the dictionary meaning of *zakroyte* (close). She emphasizes that the formation of such presuppositions is influenced by the sentence structure as well as the word's meaning. According to her, this relationship becomes apparent when a word is removed or altered within the sentence.

RESEARCH AND DISCUSSIONS

There are several linguistic mechanisms and structures used to express presuppositions in language. These ways of expressing presuppositions help convey implicit information that is assumed to be known or accepted by both the speaker and listener. Here are some of the key ways presuppositions can be expressed:

a) Definite descriptions - definite descriptions presuppose the existence of the entity being referred to. By using a definite article (the), the speaker implies that both the speaker and listener are aware of the entity's existence.

Example: "The King of France is bald." (Presupposition: There is a King of France).

b) Factive verbs - factive verbs presuppose the truth of the clause that follows them. These verbs introduce information that is assumed to be true. Common factive verbs include: know, regret, realize, be aware, discover, etc. For example: "She knows that the meeting is tomorrow." (Presupposition: The meeting is tomorrow)

c) Change of state verbs - verbs that indicate a change of state presuppose that a particular state existed before the change. Common change-of-state verbs include stop, start, continue, resume, begin, finish, etc. For example: "He stopped smoking." (Presupposition: He used to smoke.)

d) Iterative expressions - iterative words or expressions indicate that something has happened before or more than once. Words like again, return, repeat, etc. presuppose the repetition of an event. For example: "John did it again." (Presupposition: John has done it before.)

e) Cleft sentences - these constructions often presuppose a certain fact or assumption. Sentences like "It is X that Y" or "What X did was Y" presuppose some underlying information. For example: "It was Mary who broke the vase." (Presupposition: Someone broke the vase)

f) Wh-questions - presuppose the existence of an answer or the truth of the topic being questioned. They implicitly assume that there is a fact related to the question. For example: "Who broke the window?" (Presupposition: Someone broke the window.)

Comparatives also presuppose the existence of a baseline for comparison. They assume that the subject being compared already possesses a certain quality or that something else can serve as a point of reference. For instance: "John is taller than Mike." (Presupposition: Mike is tall (to some extent)).

g) Temporal clauses - they introduced by temporal conjunctions such as before, after, since, when, and until presuppose that certain events have already occurred. For instance: "Before she graduated, she worked in a cafe." (Presupposition: She graduated.). Concessive clauses, introduced by words such as even though or although, presuppose the truth of the information in the concessive clause. By way of example, "Even though John was late, the meeting started on time." (Presupposition: John was late.)

Possessive constructions presuppose the existence of the possessor and the possessed object: "Her dog is friendly." (Presupposition: She has a dog.)

Conditionals presuppose that the premise is not true. They usually take the form of "if" clauses that talk about hypothetical or unreal situations: "If I had known, I would have called you."

(Presupposition: I did not know.)

Adverbial phrases like still and already presuppose that a particular situation was true before and is either continuing (in the case of still) or has recently changed (in the case of already). Example: “She is still working on her thesis.” (Presupposition: She has been working on her thesis for some time.)

Negation and Affirmation are also given by presuppositions. Both negative and affirmative statements can carry presuppositions. For example, the statement “He didn’t stop smoking” still presupposes that he used to smoke.

In some cases, presuppositions are expressed based on shared cultural knowledge or common ground between the speaker and listener, without being overtly stated: “Let’s meet at the usual place.” (Presupposition: There is a known place where they usually meet).

CONCLUSION

It is understood that the dictionary meaning of a lexeme in the Uzbek language or the semantic that makes it up the presupposition is expressed in the sentence through the components.

In conclusion, presupposition is an essential aspect of language that helps convey implicit meanings based on shared knowledge or assumptions between the speaker and listener. The different ways in which presuppositions are expressed—through lexical meanings, factive verbs, change-of-state verbs, iterative expressions, and more—highlight the depth of linguistic structures that carry these underlying meanings. In the Uzbek language, the meaning of a lexeme or its components can play a key role in forming presuppositions within sentences. Understanding these presuppositional mechanisms is crucial for analyzing language pragmatically, as it provides insights into how meaning is constructed beyond what is explicitly stated.

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